

Digital tools for Nature-Based Solutions: a systematic qualitative analysis of acceptability and barriers for implementation

E. R. Giuffrida^{*a}, L. Sciuto^{**}, G. L. Cirelli^{**}, A. L. Popartan^{***}, A. Rizzo^{****}, T. Graziano^{**} and F. Licciardello^{**}

^{*} PhD program in Agricultural, Food and Environmental Science – Di3A, University of Catania, Via Santa Sofia 100, 95123, Catania, Italy (Emanuela.giuffrida@phd.unict.it)

^{**} Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (Di3A), University of Catania, Via Santa Sofia 100, 95123, Catania, Italy (feliciana.licciardello@unict.it; giuseppe.cirelli@unict.it; liviana.sciuto@unict.it; teresa.graziano@unict.it)

^{***} LEQUIA, Institute of the Environment, University of Girona (UdG), Carrer de Maria Aurèlia Capmany i Farnés, 69, 17003, Girona, Spain (luciaalexandra.popartan@udg.edu)

^{****} IRIDRA Srl, Via Alfonso la Marmora, 51, 5012, Firenze, Italy (rizzo@iridra.com)

^a Corresponding author: E-mail address: Emanuela.giuffrida@phd.unict.it

Abstract

This research conducts a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and strategies involved in implementing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) using software-based content analyses (such as ATLAS.ti). It focuses on the Mediterranean context and identifies major barriers, such as cultural resistance and spatial limitations, while also highlighting effective strategies, like digital tools and community engagement, in facilitating the adoption of NBS.

Keywords

ATLAS.ti, Digital Tools, Nature-Based Solutions, Participatory approaches, Public acceptance, Qualitative Research

INTRODUCTION

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) represent an innovative and essential approach to address pressing contemporary social and environmental challenges, including climate change, urbanization, and sustainable management of natural resources (Moglia et al 2021, Bauduceau et al 2015). NBS harness natural processes and cycles to create or enhance ecological infrastructures and services, providing multidimensional benefits across social, environmental, and economic spheres (Cohen-Shacham et al, 2016). Despite their significant potential, NBS often encounters a wide range of barriers¹ (Castellar et al 2024, Wihlborg et al 2019), related to notable deficiencies among public administrators, communities, and professionals concerning the understanding of NBS and the skills required for effective implementation. Moreover, the fact that non-economic benefits such as human well-being and biodiversity are not adequately taken into account limits NBS implementation (Viti et al 2022). Advanced digital tools and technologies for NBS planning, monitoring, and management are increasingly used, introducing new challenges, such as digital literacy among stakeholders, integration of diverse datasets, and development and maintenance of digital platform technical complexities (Hansen et al., 2021). In this framework, the CARDIMED² project is devoted to enhancing climate resilience in the Mediterranean by coordinating efforts across 10 regions and 28 communities. Among 9 DEMO sites implemented in the project, DEMO4 focuses on Catania city (Sicily, Italy), where a focus group and interviews were conducted. This study explores Design Thinking (Chasanidou et al., 2015) and collects data via focus group complemented by interviews for implementing digital tools to plan new NBS and monitor those existing in Mediterranean area. The study tests 4 digital tools to manage data from satellites,

¹ Green Infrastructures to mitigate Flood risks in Urban and sub-urban areas and to Improve the quality of rainwater Discharges, <https://www.gifluid.eu/>

² Climate Adaptation and Resilience Demonstrated In the MEDiterranean region, <https://www.cardimed-project.eu/>

After the focus group, six interviews were performed with key participants and the emerging data was analyzed using ATLAS.ti software, exploring themes such as barriers, strategies, and emotions related to the integration of NBS using digital tools to the Mediterranean context, where challenges such as fragmented responsibilities and cultural resistance to green infrastructure were prominent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first roundtable discussed the “scenario-based impact assessment interface” tool, responding to the total of the questions with "absolutely necessary", "necessary", and "useful" for 55%, 14% and 31%, respectively, and thus revealing a strong interest in the interface that allows data access and knowledge transfer to the public. The roundtable highlighted also negative issues like limited access to historical data and planimetric documents in Sicily, due to both inadequate monitoring and lack of data digitalization by the region. The second roundtable analysed the "CR dashboard & data storytelling" tool, evaluating it with 90% of answers within "absolutely necessary" and "necessary" categories. Experts highlighted potential benefits for app users and stressed the need to engage schools in order to broadly raise awareness among students and citizens. The third roundtable evaluated the "Citizen engagement app and intervention content management" tool, giving "absolutely necessary" "necessary", and "useful" answers in the 41%, 23% and 36%, respectively over the total cases. The initial brainstorming phase highlighted potential local applications within the Catania municipality, suggesting customization of features for different demographic targets, such as virtual reality (VR) levels (advanced for young and basic for elderly people). The VR functions were primarily proposed for planning and risk visualization tasks, that it could be used by local authorities, civic groups, and academic institutions to prevent misuse. The fourth roundtable examined the “NBS exploitation and transferability modules” tool, emphasizing a clear prioritization of features, with responses rated as "absolutely necessary" achieving a score of 53%, significantly higher than those classified as "necessary" (28%) and "useful" (18%). Experts highlighted the importance of integrating a bottom-up approach in the planning and execution of NBS strategies.

Figure 2 Prioritization analysis of focus group responses across four digital tools related to NBS

The in-depth interviews with key stakeholders from the focus group constituted the second part of the research and placed the study in a wider context. Thus, according to the interviewees, a successful digitalization of NBS should overcome important barriers, such as the difficulty of integrating NBS in “densely populated urban areas” which is due to established infrastructure and limited space for new green initiatives (interview with freelancer from Catania, aged about 50 years). In addition, there is a considerable concern about “cultural and institutional resistance to the adoption of innovative approaches such as NBS, because conventional civil engineering strategies remain deeply entrenched. Thus, it is necessary to implement more bottom-up planning approaches in order to overcome existing barriers”; this opinion was expressed by a 30-year-old researcher from Catania. Figure 3 represents a summary of recurring themes discussed in the focus group, categorized across technical and non-technical variables regarding barriers, strategies, and emotions topics.

Figure 3 Overview of strategies, emotions, and barriers in NBS implementation

CONCLUSIONS

This study used software-based content analyses to shed light on the complex dynamics surrounding NBS implementation in urban settings and the importance of leveraging digital tools to improve NBS planning and management. Digital platforms can facilitate better stakeholder engagement through interactive data visualization and analysis tools, making the benefits and capabilities of NBS more understandable and accessible to both policymakers and the public. The strategic use of digital tools promoting transparency, participation, and informed decision-making is crucial to address existing barriers. Future research should verify user feedback in relation to the field use of specific digital tools for quantifying the benefits of NBS and monitoring of their operation processes.

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